

PROBLEMS OF UNITY OF THE PEOPLE IN THE WORK OF MAHMUD KASHGARI "DIVAN LUGAT AT-TURK"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7460934>

"Divan lugat at-turk" ("Bureau of Turkic Words") is an encyclopedic work by Mahmud Kashgari on Turkic languages (1071-72). In this work, valuable information was written about the Turkic tribes, their social status, language, history, geography, metrology and astronomy of the region that inhabited Central Asia and the territory of western China in the 2nd half of the 11th century "Divan Lugat at-turk" ("The Office of Tuigk words") — an encyclopedic work Mahmud Kashgari on Turkic languages (1071-72). In this work, valuable information was written about the Turkic tribes, their social status, language, history, geography, metrology and astronomy of this region, who inhabited Central Asia and the territory of western China in the 2nd half of the 11th century. The manuscript "Divan lugat at-turk" was found in 1914 in the Turkish city of Diyorbakr. This 319-page manuscript is kept in Istanbul. This copy was copied in 1266 by the secretary of Muhammad ibn Abu Bakr ibn Fatihal-Sowi al-Damascus from a copy written in his own hand by Mahmud Koshgari, almost 200 years after the writing of "Diwan lugat at-Turk".

"Divan lugat at-turk" was written in Arabic, Arabic movements were used to correctly pronounce more than 8 thousand Turkish words. In this, of course, the author had much more difficulties, since it was impossible to convey Turkish sounds with an Arabic letter and hints of Alif, WWII, yo). For elongated and short vowels in the Turkic language, soft and hard sounds, Mahmud Kashgari uses special signs (movements) or indicates an elongation at the beginning of a word with two aliffs, or puts 2 different signs on two different words to be pronounced: azukluk, put both decimal and damma. The sign on the letters Z and R in the words of the Arabic letter b-n interpreted and described the Turkish pronunciation, which cannot be shown, in "Divan lugat at-turk". In "Divan lugat at-turk" nouns are interpreted first, then verbs. The word order was carried out depending on the average course of the letters in their composition (from 2 letters to 7 letters).

Mahmud Kashgari attached to the "Divan Lugat at-Turk" a map of the world (the image of the world in the form of a circle), which he compiled. The names of the country, city, village, mountain, desert, pass, sea, lake, river, etc. are written on the map. A number of names left unscripted on the map were interpreted in the text of the work. The map basically corresponds to the current Eastern Hemisphere. The work provides detailed information about cities, villages, the sea, lakes, Turkic tribes and seeds of the 11th century, about the social behavior of seeds, origin, name, categories of internal properties of seeds, their location, traditions, language features. In addition, animals and plants related to their name also have astronomical data, information about the zodiac and much more. In "Divan lugat at-turk" linguistic information is given in much more detail, especially in relation to the tribe and clan. At the same time, the meanings of each word (polysemy, homonym, synonym, antonym and

archaic words) are deeply analyzed, referring to the etymology of certain words. The nickname of sounds (phonemes) is much more perfect: vowels and consonant phonemes, elongated and short vowels, their pronunciation and spelling in semitones, phonetic phenomena and patterns in the language are explained in detail. In the field of morphology, the categories of words, according to the tradition of that period, are divided into 3 categories of words: verb, noun, connecting element, indicating the ways in which they are formed and stand. The "Divan lugat at-turk" presents more than 250 proverbs and sayings, dozens of poetic passages.

V. V. Bartold widely used the Devonian Turkic dictionary in his scientific work, as shown by orientalist S. Volynsky. Linguist V. I. Belyaev writes about "Divan Lugat at-turk": "We should give this work an extremely high assessment, since it is not written from books, but is based on personal observation of living material. The data of archaeological discoveries given by the author confirm most of this information." The German orientalist K. Brockelmann translated the work "Divan Lugat at-turk" into German in 1928. A photocopy of the manuscript "Divan lugat at-turk" was translated and published in Istanbul by Kilisli Rifat (3 volumes; 1915-17), and then by Besim Atalay (3 volumes; 1939-41) into Turkish. The next reissue of "Divan Lugat at-turk" in ningturktil was carried out in 1957. "Devonian Dictionary-Turk" was translated into Uzbek for the second time and published in Tashkent in 1960-63 with important comments and interpretations in 3 volumes in the publishing house "Nauka". This was the result of 35 years of work by a linguist, Doctor of Philology, Professor Salih Mutalibov. This publication is not only a translation, but also an interpretation of the attitude to translation from Turkish, prices, terms, names of people, names of cities and toponyms. The preface to the Uzbek edition contains information about the philologists of the 11th century, the work "Kutadgu bilig", the linguistic views of Mahmud Kashgari, the Turkic tribes, their formation, these clans and tribes, the relationship of languages to the current Turkic peoples and their language, transcription of translation. At the end of the Uzbek edition of "Divan Lugat at-Turk", detailed information about the Turkic clan, tribe, cities, etc. is given, in each volume of the work there are links in which the words and phrases encountered are widely described and interpreted. One of the most important aspects of the Uzbek edition is its performance, compiled on the basis of each volume. In it, the words found in "Divan Lugat at-turk" are listed in alphabetical order and the translation of the word in Uzbek and Russian is given. It is indicated on which pages of this word "Divan lugat at-turk" (first Uzbek, then a page, a line of Turkish publications).

References:

- 1.Национальная энциклопедия Узбекистана.
2. BA Kurbanovna. Trends in parliamentary effectiveness in ensuring the development of society. Восточно-европейский научный журнал, 33-36, 2020
3. BA Kurbanovna. Development And Role Of Representative Authority In The Development Of Society, Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching 2, 113-117, 2021
4. JI Baxytovna. Science in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. European journal of business startups and open society 2 (3), 82-85, 2022
5. IB Jollibekova. Training of personel in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the years of Independence. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan 2 (2), 104-108, 2019

6.IB Jolibekova. International Relations in the field of education in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan 2 (2), 93-99, 2018

7.ИБ Жоллыбекова. Вопросы оценки образования в современных условиях. атериалы международной научно-практической конференции 1 (2), 69-71, 2017

8.IB Jolibekova. Features of the development of International economic relations Republic of Karakalpakstan at the present stage. I International Conference on Suistanble Development and Economics 1 (1 ..., 2017)

9.IB Jolibekova. Peculiarities of development of international economic relations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Europe Applied Science. Europaiche Fachhochshule 1 (1), 400-402, 2015

